

5. M. M. PATEL, M. R. PATEL and B.N. MANKAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, LIII, 454.
6. M. R. PATEL, *Ph.D. Thesis*, Sardar Patel University, 1965.
7. L. J. BLLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", John Wiley and Sons Inc., New York, 1959, p. 102.
8. L. E. GODYCKI and R. E. RUNDLE, *Acta. Crystallogr.*, 1953, 6, 487.
9. E. FRASSON, R. BARDI and S. BEZZI, *Acta. Crystallogr.*, 1959, 12, 201.
10. E. O. SCHLEMPER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 1130.
11. M. A. JARSKI and E. C. LINGAFELTER, *Acta. Crystallogr.*, 1964, 17, 109.
12. H. STERK and E. ZIEGLER, *Monatsch Chem.*, 1966, 97, 1131.
13. K. NAKANISCHI, *Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy*, Nankodo Company Limited, Tokyo, 1964, p. 45.

Kinetics and Mechanism of Hydrolysis of Sec. Amyl Bromide in Neutral Medium

VIJAI SWAROOP and DHARAM PRAKASH*

Chemical Laboratories, Directorate of Geology and Mining, (U.P.), 2-Way Road, (27/4, Ram Mohan Rai Marg), Lucknow (U.P.), India.

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FEW compounds,^{1,3,4,5,6,7} in the alkyl halide series, have been investigated to show the olefin elimination kinetically independent of simultaneous substitution in alkaline medium, but the literature regarding the studies to show the kinetic dependence of olefin elimination and substitution processes which occur simultaneously in the solvolysis of halides is scanty. The present investigation mainly deals with the kinetic dependence of both processes which simultaneously occur in neutral hydrolysis of sec-amyl bromide. Olefin elimination and simultaneous substitution reactions both followed first order with respect to the halide. Total first order rate constant has been split up into its constituents (Olefin elimination and substitution rate constant) by suitable measurement of olefin formed. The present investigation also includes the effect of change in the composition of the medium on the rate of reactions, calculation of separate energies of activation in both processes, effect of salt on rate of reaction. In the present case, the unimolecular processes may take place through the scheme given by Moelwyn-Hughes and Fells⁸.

Experimental

Sec-amyl bromide was dried over anhydrous sodium carbonate and calcium chloride and then fractionated. The fraction collected at 11 °-118° (B.P.) was used for all measurements.

The value of first order rate constant was determined by estimating the acid produced as a result of hydrolysis of halide at various intervals of time and by

employing the usual integrated formula for first order. The olefin was estimated by the following method. The sealed ampule containing 5 ml. of the reaction mixture was first cooled and then broken by shaking under water at 0° in an evacuated stoppered flask provided with an inlet and outlet tube, the former reaching the bottom. The flask was kept at 50°-60° in a water bath and the whole amount of olefin produced was swept by passing a slow stream of nitrogen and bubbling the gas in a flask containing a known amount of bromine in carbon tetrachloride. The remaining bromine was estimated by titrating it against standard thiosulphate. The substitution product was identified as sec-amyl alcohol by the method described earlier.^{8,4,5,6,7,10}

Results and Discussions

Experimental results are presented in Tables 1-2. Table 1 records the total first order rate constant

TABLE 1

Temperature (°C)	[EtOH-H ₂ O] (V/V %)	[KBr] × M	k', in min. ⁻¹ Limits of accuracy are ±2.7% or less. k', × 10 ⁵
[Sec-amyl bromide] = 7.97 × 10 ⁻³ M			
55	80	—	1.82
"	75	—	4.84 ^a
"	70	—	7.60
"	65	—	9.11 ^a
"	60	—	23.85
"	55	—	95.02
"	50	—	143.66 ^a
"	45	—	201.44
"	40	—	262.61
"	60	0.25	23.00
"	"	0.50	21.85 ^b
"	"	0.75	20.62 ^b
"	"	1.00	19.24
"	"	1.25	17.92
"	"	1.50	15.67 ^b
40	"	—	4.37 ^c
45	"	—	8.12 ^a
50	"	—	12.74
60	"	—	38.56 ^d
65	"	—	64.60 ^c
70	"	—	107.72 ^d
75	"	—	170.18 ^d

a: ±2.5%, b: ±1.2%, c: ±2.8%, d: ±3.6%.

* For correspondence.

TABLE 2

[Sec - amyl bromide] = 7.97×10^{-3} M[EtOH - H₂O] = 60% V/V

Experiment	Temperature (°C)	E ₁ (%)	SN ₁ (%)	$\frac{S_{N_1}}{S_{N_1} + E_1}$	$\frac{E_1}{S_{N_1} + E_1}$	k' ₁ × 10 ⁵ min ⁻¹	k' ₁ S × 10 ⁵ min ⁻¹	k' ₁ E × 10 ⁵ min ⁻¹
1	75	5.90	94.10	0.9410	0.0590	170.18	160.14	10.04
2	70	5.73	94.27	0.9427	0.0573	107.72	101.55	6.17
3	65	5.55	94.45	0.9445	0.0555	64.60	61.01	3.59
4	60	5.41	94.59	0.9459	0.0541	38.56	36.47	2.09

obtained under various physical conditions, mentioned in columns 1, 2 and 3. The increase in the velocity of first order process on addition of water to the reaction mixture is in accordance with the findings of Eliel et al⁸ and the theory of solvent action⁹. The decrease in the first order rate constant by an initial addition of potassium bromide may be attributed to the decrease in the nucleophilic activity of water molecules associated with the increase of ionic strength of the medium.

The percentage of olefin obtained in the unimolecular process (shown in column 3 of table 2) are the average of at least three observations. E₁ and SN₁ terms stand for the reactions occurring through unimolecular elimination and unimolecular substitution processes. The fractions contained in columns 5 and 6 were averages of observations taken at various intervals of time and they were almost constant which shows that these fractions actually represent the ratios in which the total unimolecular process has been rightly split up into unimolecular substitution and elimination processes. These factors of columns 5 and 6 of table 2 will give the rate constants for unimolecular substitution and elimination respectively (columns 8 and 9) on multiplication with total unimolecular rate constant (column 7). A perusal of table 2 shows that unimolecular substitution is faster than unimolecular elimination which may be attributed to predominance of inductive effect (responsible for former) over electrometric effect (responsible for latter).

The values of energy of activation for unimolecular substitution, unimolecular elimination and total unimolecular reaction come out to be 23.12, 24.57 and 22.06 kcal/mole respectively. The corresponding values of entropy of activation for above reactions have been worked out to be -15.19, -16.44 and -18.28 e.u. respectively.

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References

1. E. D. HUGHES, C. K. INGOLD and U. G. SHAPIRO, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 225.
2. E. A. MOELWYN-HUGHES and I. FELLS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 398.
3. BHARAT SINGH, KUNJ BEHARI and BAL KRISHNA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, 22, 137.
4. KUNJ BEHARI and BAL KRISHNA, *Chimie. Analytique.*, 1969, 51, (No. 2), 87.
5. BHARAT SINGH, VIJAI SWAROOP and BAL KRISHNA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 44-46.
6. B. SINGH, V. SWAROOP, A. K. SRIVASTAVA and B. KRISHNA, *Acta Chimica Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae, Tomus*, 1975, 86(3), 279-284.
7. BHARAT SINGH, VIJAI SWAROOP, ARUN KUMAR SRIVASTAVA and BAL KRISHNA, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, 1, 1975, 1, (no. 2), 89.
8. E. L. ELIEL and R. S. RO, *Tetrahedron*, 1958, 42, 355.
9. E. D. HUGHES and C. K. INGOLD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 252.
10. BHARAT SINGH, VIJAI SWAROOP, A. K. SRIVASTAVA, MEENAKSHI RICHARDS and BAL KRISHNA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 1155-1158.

Phosphate Release from Basic Slags by EDTA

D. N. PATHAK

Department of Chemistry,
Regional Institute of Technology,
Jamshedpur.

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WALLACE and coworkers¹ studied the use of metal chelates as a source of micronutrient supply to plants. Das² in a recent publication suggested the possibility of using zinc-EDTA as a combined micronutrient fertilizer and soil iron mobilizer. Of late Hajra and Chakravarti³ advocated the use of some chelating agents to release phosphate from minerals.